

ISSN 1592-1638

Vol. 17 • N. 1 • March 2015

Heroin Addiction and Related Clinical Problems

Periodico trimestrale - Sped. in Abb. Post. - D.L. 353/2003 conv. in L. 27/02/2004 n° 46 art. 1, comma 1, DCB PISA - Aut. tirb. di Pisa n.5 del 9-3-2000

the official journal of

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Regular article

Heroin Addict Relat Clin Probl 2015; 17(1): 73-78

HEROIN ADDICTION &
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Consequences of cardiac toxicity in patients on low methadone doses during methadone maintenance treatment

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Summary

Background. Methadone has been extensively studied and prescribed worldwide in the methadone maintenance treatment (MMT) of opiate addicts. However, methadone-induced prolongation of the corrected QT (QTc) interval has been reported, and it could be associated with torsades de pointes (TdP). In cases of more persistent TdP, ventricular fibrillation leading to cardiac arrest and sudden death could develop. **Aim.** We report the consequences of cardiac toxicity in two patients who were receiving low doses of methadone (≤ 60 mg), along with diazepam as the main adjunctive therapy. Surprisingly, one patient developed malignant arrhythmia and the other one died at the very start of MMT. **Case Presentations.** A 28-year-old male died at the very start of MMT while receiving low doses of methadone (30 mg/day), diazepam (30 mg) and clozapine (25 mg). The forensic pathologist who reported his death classified it as being methadone-related, with signs of acute lung oedema of cardiac origin and myocardial changes. A 37-year-old male on a low methadone dose (60 mg/day) and diazepam (30 mg) developed significant QTc prolongation and malignant arrhythmia during triple antibiotic therapy (gentamicin, ceftriaxone, metronidazole) of phlegmon of the lower limb. After treatment at the Intensive Care Unit and the discontinuation of methadone and diazepam, a regular cardiac function was restored. **Conclusions.** It is highly advisable for health care professionals to be cautious in prescribing benzodiazepines and other drugs, even when patients are on low MMT doses. Significant QTc prolongation, followed by the development of potentially fatal arrhythmia in opiate addicts on low-dose MMT is more likely to occur when several concomitant factors are acting simultaneously.

Key Words: Methadone; drug-drug interaction; QTc prolongation; torsades de pointes; sudden death

1. Introduction

Methadone has been extensively studied and prescribed worldwide in the treatment of opiate addiction and the management of chronic pain [12].

However, the methadone-induced prolongation of corrected QT (QTc) interval has been reported [3, 7, 11, 14, 22, 23]. The underlying mechanism of drug-induced QTc prolongation is the blockade of delayed rectifier K⁺ current encoded by the human ether-à gogo related gene (hERG) and it could be associated with torsades de pointes (TdP) [2, 6].

In cases of more persistent TdP, ventricular fibrillation leading to cardiac arrest and sudden death could develop [11].

More than 90% of cases of drug-induced TdP occur with QTc values over 500 ms [10]. Considering the most recently published guidelines, dose reduction or discontinuation of the offending drug should be considered when the QTc interval is 470-500 ms for males, and 480-500 ms for females, or when the QTc interval increases by at least 60 ms from pretreatment values. If the QTc interval is ≥ 500 ms, the offending drug should be discontinued [24].

According to the previously published data, risk factors for TdP during methadone maintenance treatment (MMT) include: high-dose methadone treatment (>100 mg/day), electrolyte abnormalities, pre-existing heart disease, liver failure, renal insufficiency, concomitant treatment with QT-prolonging and/or P450-inhibiting drugs, female gender as well as genetic predisposition [10, 18].

Despite the fact that most health care professionals were aware of methadone's possible depressant effect on respiration, a large-scale study conducted in the USA revealed that ventricular arrhythmia and cardiac arrest were at that time the most frequent adverse events attributed to methadone that had been reported to the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) [11].

The top 10 most frequently used medications associated with QTc prolongation during MMT included antiretroviral drugs, benzodiazepines and antibiotics [11]. In addition, Darke et al. showed that methadone-related deaths were significantly more likely to be diagnosed with cardiac pathology, and with benzodiazepines detected in post-mortem blood samples, than with evidence of heroin toxicity [4].

In connection with the data just mentioned, we are able to report two cases of consequences deriving from cardiac toxicity in patients who were receiving low doses of methadone (≤ 60 mg), along with diazepam as their main adjunctive therapy. Surprisingly, one patient developed malignant arrhythmia, while the other one died at the very start of MMT.

2. Case presentation

2.1. Case 1

A 28-year-old male, who had been a heroin addict for 13 years, was admitted to the Department of Psychiatry in order to start on MMT. Apart from heroin, he denied using any additional psychoactive substances; he also stated he had never taken a heroin overdose. With the exception of hepatitis C and opiate addiction, his past medical history did not include any other diseases. Curiosity had been his main reason for beginning to abuse drugs. He denied drinking alcohol, but admitted smoking 1 pack of cigarettes/day. As for his family health history, both of his parents had suffered from hypertension, while none of his close relatives had suffered from arrhythmias or died from sudden cardiac arrest. He was the only child and lived with his parents, who only found out about his problems with drug abuse after he had been addicted for 4 years.

After a 3-day detoxification with tramadol, and before the initiation of MMT, he underwent an ECG, which revealed a sinus rhythm with QTc of 420 ms (Fig. 1a). Blood pressure was 130/80 mmHg. The complete blood count was within the normal range. Initial electrolytes were as follows: sodium 144 mmol/l (135-155 mmol/l), potassium 4.6 mmol/l (3.5-5.5 mmol/l), chloride 103 mmol/l (98-112 mmol/l). The blood urea nitrogen level was 5.8 mmol/l (2.5-7.5 mmol/l) and the creatinine level was 80 μ mol/l (30-98 μ mol/l). Liver function tests showed an AST level of 56 U/l (5-37 U/l) and an ALT level of 147 U/l (5-40 U/l).

The alkaline phosphatase level was 107 U/l (30-115 U/l) and the total bilirubin level was 13 μ mol/l (3-21 μ mol/l). During the detoxification period, along with tramadol, he was treated with 30 mg of diazepam and 25 mg of clozapine. On the 4th day of his hospitalization, tramadol was replaced by methadone (starting dose was 20 mg/day, followed by 30 mg/day), while additional treatment remained the same for the next four days. Early in the morning on the 8th day of his hospitalization he was found dead in his bed.

Going on now to review the toxicological findings, methadone, diazepam and clozapine were detected in the post-mortem blood sample within the therapeutic range (at concentrations of 0.0415 μ g/ml, 0.0857 μ g/ml, and 0.0459 μ g/ml, respectively). As to the pathohistological findings in the heart tissue samples, signs of acute and recent phenomena (contractive band necrosis, convoluted fibres, granulation tissue), as well as chronic ones (fatty infiltration, subepicardial perivascular fibrosis, hypertrophy of myocardial fibres) were recognizable. In the liver, signs of chronic persistent viral hepatitis could be observed, too. In the lungs there were signs of oedema of cardiac origin – a finding that was supported by the presence of haemosiderophages. In the forensic pathologist's report, this death was classified as being methadone-related.

2.2. Case 2

A 37-year-old male, a former injection drug user on MMT, was making his second attempt to end heroin use. He had first entered MMT two years previously. He had reached 90 mg methadone/day before he decided to stop using it, and the side-effects of methadone had not been blamed for that decision. Besides heroin, he confirmed having used additional psychoactive substances at times (cannabis and ben-

zodiazepines) and he had taken a heroin overdose on two occasions. He denied using cocaine and amphetamine. Apart from hepatitis C and opiate addiction, his past medical history did not include any other diseases. He was a chain smoker. As to his family health history, his mother suffered from ischaemic heart disease, while his father was an alcoholic. Like him, his younger brother was an opiate addict. None of his close relatives had had arrhythmias or died from sudden cardiac arrest.

He was admitted to the Department of Psychiatry after a witnessed collapse, which lasted about 1 min and occurred one hour after the patient had ingested his regular methadone dose of 60 mg in the outpatient MMT centre. Along with methadone, the patient took 30 mg of diazepam each day. After being admitted to the Department of Psychiatry, the patient looked pale, due to a phlegmon in the lower one leg. The initial treatment included triple antibiotic therapy (gentamicin, ceftriaxone, metronidazole), while the patient continued to receive his regular therapy with methadone and diazepam.

On the second day of hospitalization at the Department of Psychiatry, the patient suddenly lost consciousness, and stopped breathing. There was no palpable pulse. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation, which included external cardiac compressions and bagmask ventilation, was initiated while the resuscitation team was called. Spontaneous circulation resumed before the resuscitation team arrived. Since the patient was unstable, with respiration that was insufficient and hypotensive (70/40 mmHg), he was endotracheally intubated, ventilated and transferred to intensive care unit (ICU).

Initially, in ICU the patient was comatose, mechanically ventilated, with blood pressure of 110/70 mmHg, and heart rate of 56 beats/min. ECG revealed a sinus rhythm with a prolonged QTc interval of 539 ms (Fig. 1b). Laboratory results included a normal set of cardiac enzymes (troponin, CK-MB, and myoglobin levels). Electrolytes were as follows: sodium 138 mmol/l (135-150 mmol/l), potassium 3.5 mol/l (3.5-5.5 mmol/l) and calcium 1.25 mmol/l (1.00-1.35 mmol). The blood urea level was 22.3 mmol/l (up to 6.5 mmol/l), while the creatinine level was 117 µmol/l (62-125 µmol/l). Liver function tests showed an ALT level of 57 U/l (15-18 U/l) and an AST level of 30 U/l (17-22 U/l). The total bilirubin level was 5 µmol/l (5.9-20.5 µmol/l). The complete blood count showed: leukocytes $13.9 \times 10^9/l$ ($4-10 \times 10^9/l$), erythrocytes $3.17 \times 10^{12}/l$ ($4.2-6 \times 10^{12}/l$), haemoglobin level 85 g/l (120-160 g/l), and thrombocytes $488 \times 10^9/l$ ($130-$

$400 \times 10^9/l$). The blood glucose level was 10.4 mmol/l (2-6 mmol/l). CRP was 240 mg/l and procalcitonin was 0.41 ng/ml. The blood toxicology screening was positive and in the therapeutic range for methadone (0.414 µg/ml) and diazepam (0.038 µg/ml).

During 24-h ECG monitoring for the first two days at ICU, multifocal ventricular extrasystoles, malignant arrhythmia of TdP type, and ventricular fibrillations were repeatedly detected and terminated either spontaneously, or by applying DC shock (Fig. 1c).

Treatment at the ICU included lignocaine (80 mg i.v. bolus), magnesium sulphate (2 g i.v. bolus) as well as a triple antibiotic therapy. During mechanical ventilation, the patient was sedated with midazolam. When the patient became haemodynamically and rhythmically stable, metoprolol (25 mg t.i.d.) was introduced, while the use of magnesium and antibiotics was continued until the end of hospitalization. Methadone was discontinued and buprenorphine was initiated as an alternative. Additional treatment during his hospitalization also contained nadroxiaparine-calcium and ranitidine.

During hospitalization, *Streptococcus viridans* sensitive to most antibiotics was cultivated from the phlegmonous wound, which was cleaned and bandaged on a daily basis. After methadone and diazepam withdrawal there were no further episodes of cardiac dysrhythmia during this hospitalization. The patient was discharged from the hospital on the 12th day of hospitalization with the following treatment: cefixime (400 mg/day), buprenorphine (4 mg/day), and metoprolol (25 mg t.i.d.).

At discharge, an ECG revealed sinus rhythm with a QTc interval of 481 ms (Fig. 1d). Blood pressure was 130/80 mmHg, while pulse was 104 beats/min. Electrolyte analysis revealed sodium of 134 mmol/l, potassium of 4.2 mol/l and calcium of 1.16 mmol/l. The blood urea level was 5.7 mmol/l, while the creatinine level was 55 µmol/l. Liver function tests showed an ALT level of 29 U/l and an AST level of 48 U/l. The total bilirubin level was 7.4 µmol/l. The complete blood count showed: leukocytes $9.8 \times 10^9/l$, erythrocytes $3.34 \times 10^{12}/l$, haemoglobin level 104 g/l, and thrombocytes $332 \times 10^9/l$. The blood glucose level was 6.2 mmol/l.

3. Discussion

The connection between methadone and TdP was first reported in 2002, followed by a clinical practice guideline in 2009 recommending QTc inter-

Figure 1. Electrocardiogram revealing: a) QTc of 420 ms; b) QTc of 539 ms; c) torsades de pointes; d) QTc of 481 ms.

val screening in methadone treatment [14, 15]. As far as we know, the connection between low methadone doses (≤ 60 mg/day) together with concomitantly used diazepam, clozapine or other cited antibiotics, and cardiac arrest or ventricular arrhythmia in MMT patients has not been previously assessed.

Pre-existing cardiac diseases or changes could be a risk factor for drug-induced TdP [10]. In contrast to the malignant arrhythmia detected in the patient described as Case 2, no heart rhythm changes were recorded in the patient described as Case 1, even though both these patients were on low therapeutic doses of methadone. The post-mortem pathohistological findings were consistent with the data recently published by Darke et al. in reporting cardiac changes in methadone- or heroin-related deaths, emphasizing, however, rather the role of substances consumed concomitantly by opiate addicts (particularly benzodiazepines, cannabis, cocaine, tricyclic antidepressants) than heroin or methadone alone [4, 5]. Methadone cardiac adverse effects in methadone-related deaths can be confirmed pathohistologically in a form of acute myocardial damage as well [20]. In addition, methadone has negative chronotropic properties, and it has been observed that drug-induced TdP is often triggered during periods of bradycardia [10], which had been recorded in Case 2 before that patient had

been admitted to the ICU.

Although most previous studies reported a positive correlation between methadone dose and QTc interval in individuals receiving a dose of 100 mg or higher [7, 9, 14, 21], Chang et al. discovered that low-dose methadone therapy (median daily dose < 60 mg) was in a dose-dependent correlation with QTc interval and associated with significant QTc lengthening within 6 months of treatment initiation [3]. Furthermore, Roy et al. showed that drug-induced QTc prolongation was evident in patients receiving relatively low daily doses of methadone (80.4 ± 27.5 mg), with no evidence of a dose-response relationship [23]. According to Perrin-Terrin et al., in 7 cases of sudden death, the exact cause of the death and the QTc values were not completely elucidated, but the methadone blood concentrations were within therapeutic range, and all the patients were treated for opiate addiction with the usual range of daily dose (40-80 mg). Moreover, in most cases, death occurred at the beginning of MMT, during the adaptation of dose regimen [22]. This is in full accordance with the findings in Case 1. It should be mentioned that Krantz et al. described 17 patients who had TdP while taking a very high dose of methadone (mean daily methadone dose was 397 ± 283 mg) [14]. Given all these facts, QTc prolongation, cardiac arrhythmias and sudden cardiac death

have been described in patients receiving both low and very high doses.

Taking into account other drugs used concomitantly with methadone, clozapine alone is rarely associated with prolongation of the QTc interval, but it may contribute to pathological QTc prolongation in patients with other risk factors for this condition [19]. It has not been previously reported that antibiotics used in Case 2 (metronidazole, gentamicin) increase the risk of TdP in patients taking methadone, but metronidazole can facilitate such cardiac adverse effect if it is combined with other QTc-prolonging drugs (e.g. amiodarone, quinidine) [12, 13]. On the other hand ceftriaxone is among top 10 most frequently reported concomitant medications for QTc prolongation or TdP in the USA [11]. Many benzodiazepines are metabolic substrates of CYP3A4 and thus they are also considered as weak competitive inhibitors of CYP3A4 [12]. Lintzeris et al. indicated that pharmacodynamic interactions of benzodiazepines and opioids on the respiratory system can produce a potentially lethal outcome [17].

Toxicological and clinical findings of methadone and benzodiazepines, both in therapeutic concentrations, together with the latest in vitro results suggest their additive action which increases cardiac risk in concurrent treatment. The authors found that concomitant administration of diazepam alters the effect of methadone on cardiac channels through an interaction at Na⁺ channels rather than via additive effects on K⁺ ones [16]. In addition, methadone is a chiral drug with two enantiomeric forms: (R)-methadone, which is primarily associated with the drug's pharmacological activity and (S)-methadone, which has limited pharmacological activity, but a higher potential for blocking the hERG K⁺ channel.

Recently published data suggest that CYP2B6 slow metabolizer status is associated with high (S)- but not (R)-methadone plasma concentrations which may subsequently induce QTc interval prolongation [6].

The possible genetic predisposition of patients in terms of the existence of congenital long QT syndrome (LQTS) was not evaluated in our study. Thus, the LQTS carrier status is often unknown to individuals and clinicians prior to risk exposure and subsequent clinical manifestation [1].

Poor general condition, dehydration, intoxication, anaemia, liver and renal impairment, uncontrolled blood glucose level could be additional factors that contribute to drug-induced arrhythmia [8, 10].

5. Conclusions

In opiate addicts on MMT, significant QTc prolongation, followed by the development of potentially fatal arrhythmia is more likely to occur when several concomitant factors are acting simultaneously [10]. Moreover, it is highly advisable for health care professionals to be cautious in prescribing benzodiazepines, clozapine and certain antibiotics to methadone users, as well as performing a thorough physical examination of MMT patients.

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Acknowledgements

Authors thank Anthony Johnson for the language revision.

Role of the funding source

The Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Serbia (grants number III 41012 and OI 172050) supported this research work.

Contributors

All authors contributed equally to this study.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.